

Exploring international atmospherics. The impact on shopping behaviors based on the language of the lyrics of music played in global apparel retailers' stores

M. Paz Toldos (corresponding author)

Tecnologico de Monterrey, Mexico.

mariadelapaz.toldos@tec.mx

Eva M. González

Tecnologico de Monterrey, Mexico.

Scott Motyka

Keck Graduate Institute, Claremont, California, USA

Abstract

Purpose – Previous research has demonstrated that, in retail settings, music has some of the largest effects on consumer behavior. However, it is still unknown how the language of the lyrics (native vs foreign) affects consumer behavior. In order to address this gap in retail atmospherics, the purpose of this paper is to examine the differential effects of the language of the lyrics of the music played and explain the interactions between the music language and volume.

Design/methodology/approach – The data were obtained from a field study conducted in an apparel store and from 241 shoppers speaking Spanish as their native language. The study involved the manipulation of language of the lyrics of music played in the store (native vs foreign).

Findings – Results indicate that customers in a non-English speaking country are more likely to make purchases when music is played in English, which fits with the store's global image. This effect is mediated by time spent in the store.

Practical implications – For managers of global apparel brands, the results suggest that English music may be a good option to increase time spent in the store and subsequent purchases. This is especially attractive as music is an atmospheric cue that can be easily modified at less expense than other atmospheric cues.

Originality/value – This work is the first to demonstrate that fitting the language of the lyrics of music in an international retail store to a global brand image affects consumer behavior. Furthermore, it demonstrates that atmospherics research may not directly transfer to non-English speaking countries.

Keywords: International retailing, Atmospherics, Music, Language of the lyrics of music, Store-fit

Paper type: Research paper

Introduction

As retailing in the USA continues to experience declining revenues from brick and mortar channels (Thompson, 2017), retailers are increasingly looking to international markets for growth. A growing question that retailers continue to face as they expand internationally is whether they should adapt their store atmospherics to the local culture or have a consistent design across stores and countries.

Retailers differentiate themselves from other competitive options by designing their store environment to be pleasant to customers; one technique used is to create in store sensory experiences in an effort to increase loyalty and sales (Morrison et al., 2011; Puccinelli et al., 2009; Spence et al., 2014). This stream of research, known collectively as “retail atmospherics,” suggests broadly that the various environmental elements of a physical retail store affect consumers’ perceptions of quality and value, as well as their willingness to purchase (Roschk et al., 2017). To this end, retailers manipulate store environmental factors such as music, lighting, colour, temperature, and aroma to influence consumers’ cognitive and affective states, which in turn affect shopping behaviours (cf. Oakes and North, 2008; Roschk et al., 2017; Soars, 2009). While retail atmospherics is an active area of research, few studies consider how a retailer should customize their atmospherics internationally. To address this gap, the current study explores the effects of one of the cheapest and easiest atmospherics to customize: music. Although previous research has shown that music affects purchase decisions (Morrison et al., 2011; Oakes et al., 2013), no research, to our knowledge, has explored how the language of the lyrics (native vs foreign) of that music affects consumers. Specifically, the reported study explores how consumers in a non-native English-speaking country (i.e. Mexico) differentially responds to music played in their native language (i.e. Spanish) vs a non-native language (i.e. English).

Due to the minimal switching costs that a retailer incurs to change the music played in its stores (compared to almost any other renovation or change), marketers use music to both build a unique emotional connection with employees (Skandrani et al., 2011) and customers while also promoting sales (e.g. Jain and Bagdare, 2011). Research suggests that fitting the type of music played to a store’s environment can have positive impacts on consumer behaviors (Jacob et al., 2009; Michel et al., 2017; Vida et al., 2007). For example, Abercrombie & Fitch, Hollister, C&A, and Victoria’s Secret play specific musical styles in their stores that fit the brand’s personality as well as the general store ambiance (Kumar and Kim, 2014).

The study of music and language and their relationship have been long a subject of a wide variety of approaches (e.g. Jackendoff, 2009; Patel, 2008; Saffran, 2004). There is a parallelism between music and language, inasmuch as they are both “combinational systems” which contain acoustic elements such as words and tunes, and, although there are differences, both share some commonalities such as symbols, grammar and information transmission (Mithen, 2006). One attribute that music and language shares is that they both involve multiple levels of representation: rhythmic, melodic and

harmonic in the case of music; and phonological prosodic, lexical, semantic, syntactic and pragmatic in the case of language (Besson and Friederici, 1998). However, there are some differences; while in music the set of sounds produced simultaneously by different instruments in a combination of melody, harmony and rhythm is understandable and generates something beautiful; in the case of language this is not possible. The juxtaposition of sounds generates noise in the message. On the other hand, the number of elements and the order of them, as well as the assignment of meanings to words can vary from one language to another, which does not happen with music (Besson and Schön, 2006).

In this sense, it is important to differentiate the musical language and the music language lyrics. When we talk about the structure of musical language, we are referring to the combination of sounds (tones, melodic segments), syntax (musical grammars) and meaning of music (emotions and feelings that elicit) (see Meyer, 1956). This gives the music a flexibility and wealth that language does not have (Gómez-Ariza et al., 2000). When we talk about the language of the lyrics, we are referring to the vocal music (the most popular form of music), the song that includes the lyrics and the tune (Bonnell et al., 2001). Part of the semantic of an audio musical piece resides exclusively in its lyrics and music comes without lyrics and also with lyrics.

Lyrics are an important form of communications, lyrics tell stories and communicate with audiences in a manner similar to how people have conversations with each other (Pettijohn and Sacco, 2009). In this sense, although music in advertising has generated considerable research in marketing (e.g. Bruner, 1990; MacInnis and Park, 1991), the impact of lyrics in advertisements has received little consideration. However, some researchers have analyzed song lyrics for their content and their effect on improving ad attention and increasing the advertisement's recall (Olsen and Johnson, 2002). Also, music with lyrics can provide an atmosphere and an image (Alpert and Alpert, 1991). Despite the effects of lyrics in advertisements, little consideration has been given to the language of the lyrics (native vs foreign) on consumer behavior in retail atmospherics. This is why this research has focused on the topic of the impact of the language of the lyrics of music on shopping behaviors.

When considering the effects of store design, the most frequently investigated attributes in the atmospherics literature tend to be the musical elements of song selection (rhythm, pitch, style/genre, tempo and volume), rather than linguistic elements, such as the presence of lyrics in a language the listener may or may not be able to understand. To the authors' knowledge, no previous work has examined the role of the language of the lyrics (native vs foreign) of the music in a retailing context. As will be discussed shortly, it is reasonable to expect that there are significant differences in the effects of music as a retail atmospheric depending on whether the customer can understand the semantic content of the pieces played. In addition, other variables, such as fit with service setting (e.g. global retailer) and consumers' familiarity with the music, are also important to examine (Demoulin, 2011; Jacob et al., 2009; North et al., 2016; Spangenberg et al.,

2005; Vida et al., 2007). Finally, we examine whether the volume of music acts as a boundary condition to attenuate these effects.

The current research makes two key contributions. First, to the authors' knowledge, this is the first study to examine the differential effects of the language of the lyrics (native vs foreign) of the music played. Second, the reported research examines the interactions between the language of the lyrics of music and the volume it is played. These gaps are addressed with an experimental field study, conducted in a real-world setting (cf. Chebat and Dubé, 2000; Morrison et al., 2011). Specifically, we systematically vary the language of the lyrics (native vs foreign) and volume of music played in a retail store to test the interaction effects of both language of the lyrics and volume of music on customers' shopping behaviors (i.e. time in store and whether they made a purchase).

Conceptual framework and hypotheses

Noting the effects of environmental factors on consumers' behavior, retailers manipulate the design of their stores in an effort to influence consumers' perceptions, evaluations, behaviors and experiences at the point of purchase (Ballantine et al., 2010; Puccinelli et al., 2009).

Elements of store design are known as atmospheric stimuli (Kotler, 1973), and include temperature, lighting, layout, cleanliness, scent, color, crowding and music (Michel et al., 2017; Spence et al., 2014; Turley and Milliman, 2000). The research stream that seeks to understand how the environment (or "atmosphere") of a retail store affects customer's behaviors, then, is collectively known as "retail atmospherics" (Baker et al., 2002; Grewal et al., 2014).

Utilizing Mehrabian and Russell's (1974) environmental psychology model as a theoretical lens, researchers have examined the effects of store atmospherics, generating substantial literature about the effects of environmental stimuli on consumer behavior (Donovan and Rossiter, 1982; Donovan et al., 1994). Pleasant or enjoyable store environments encourage a number of positive consumption behaviors, including a desire to stay in and explore the store environment (Soh et al., 2015), greater store favorability (Sherman et al., 1997), greater propensity to make a purchase (Broekemier et al., 2008; Fiore et al., 2000), more money spent (Jain and Bagdare, 2011; Morrin and Chebat, 2005) and greater satisfaction with the experience (Mattila and Wirtz, 2001; Morrison et al., 2011). Among atmospherics cues, music is one of the most widely studied elements of the store environment due to the ease and low cost to change (Spence et al., 2014).

The effects of music on consumer behavior

As summarized in Table I (adapted from theoretical dimensions proposed by Michel et al. (2017), to drive consumer behavior. As such, this stream of research has examined the effects of various elements of music (e.g. tempo, volume, genre) and has covered a wide array of outcomes, such as satisfaction with the shopping experience, shopping

items, time spent in the store, sales, purchase behavior and impulsive buying (Akhter et al., 1994; Andersson et al., 2012; Donovan et al., 1994; Grossbart et al., 1990; Kellaris and Altsech, 1992; Milliman, 1982, 1986; Morrison, 2001; Ward et al., 1992; Yalch and Spangenberg, 2000). For example, research has found that consumers spend more time and spend more in stores that use music with a slow tempo (Garlin and Owen, 2006; Milliman, 1982, 1986). In related studies, researchers found that faster tempos and higher volumes affected perceptions of time spent in store and alcohol consumption in restaurants (Guéguen et al., 2008; Kellaris and Altsech, 1992). Considering store-music fit, research has shown that fitting the genre of music to the store is important – using classical music in a wine shop leads consumers to not only buy more wine, but to choose more expensive brands (Areni and Kim, 1993).

Michel et al. (2017) identify three key dimensions to predict the effects of music in a retail setting – liking/familiarity, popularity of piece and store-fit. The first, liking/familiarity, refers to the customers' overall assessment and knowledge about a musical piece. The second, popularity, describes whether a musical piece is known by a large number of people (Petruzzellis et al., 2014). The last dimension, and most relevant for the reported research, is the fit of the music to the service setting; that is, how well the chosen music piece matches consumers' expectations of the respective serving setting (Demoulin, 2011; Oakes and North, 2008a). Discussed next, store-fit is one of the most important considerations a retailer can make when choosing music, as the impact of music is affected by the relationship between music, type of business and type of clientele (Demoulin, 2011; Morrin and Chebat, 2005; North et al., 2003; Vida et al., 2007; Vida, 2008; Wilson, 2003).

Insert Table 1 here

The importance of music and store image fit

The degree of congruence between a retailer's overall brand and the music (e.g. genre, tempo) played is known as store-fit (Baker et al., 2002; Garlin and Owen, 2006; MacInnis and Park, 1991). Research has demonstrated greater store-fit leads to positive effects on time spent in store and customer's satisfaction (Oakes and North, 2008a; Vida, 2008; Vida et al., 2007; Wilson, 2003). For example, Vida et al. (2007) found that when customers perceived a good fit of the music played with the overall retail store image, they felt more comfortable, spent a prolonged period of time in the store and subsequently spent more (Vida, 2008).

Several studies suggest that likelihood to purchase/conversion rates are enhanced when the music fits the context in which it is played (North et al., 2016), and the style of music is likely to have a significant effect on customers' perceptions and choices (Bruner, 1990). When classical (vs Top 40) music is played in a wine store, consumers are more likely to buy more expensive wines that "fit" with the music (Areni and Kim, 1993; Yalch and Spangenberg, 1990), as music conveys and triggers relevant

information that primes consumers' beliefs about a product (e.g. classical music is often considered sophisticated, similar to wine, creating a fit). Similarly, Radocy and Boyle (1997) found that people are likely to spend more time and money in a restaurant or retail environment if the music is considered appropriate to the setting. Regarding the shopping experience, Morrison (2001) found that specifically programmed music can create a memorable identity for specific retail brands, can influence the perception of the uniqueness of products and services, and customers often stay longer in the store.

Given the importance of store-fit, it is interesting that researchers have yet to examine how the language of the lyrics (native vs foreign) of the music played affects store-fit and subsequent consumer behaviors. As globalization has expanded, English has become the most important language in international advertising (Gerritsen et al., 2007; Hornikx et al., 2010), as it suggests modernity, sophistication and a cosmopolitan identity (Bhatia, 2000; Piller, 2003). Where ads in one's native language elicits associations with a sense of cultural closeness, English copy elicits a sense of sophistication of the brand presented instead (Hornikx et al., 2010; Krishna and Ahluwalia, 2008; Piller, 2001). Importantly, the effectiveness of English copy is significantly stronger when there is congruence between language and product (Hendriks et al., 2015; Hornikx et al., 2013).

Extending these findings to the language of the lyrics (native vs foreign) of the music in a retail setting, we argue that, the use of English lyrics evokes a sense of modernity that creates greater store-fit with a global retailer's brand (compared to music in the native language) leading to a greater likelihood of making a purchase. We expect this fit to occur as foreign/global brands are typically perceived as fashionable and high quality (Keillor et al., 1996). Additionally, based on previous research, we expect the effects of store-fit on purchases is mediated by time spent in the store, as research suggests individuals spend more time in shops with greater store-fit (cf. Sullivan, 2002; Vida, 2008; Vida et al., 2007). Thus, we formally propose the following hypothesis:

H1. Music lyrics played in a foreign (English) language (vs native language) will lead to greater time spent in the store and greater likelihood to make a purchase.

H2. Total time spent in store mediates the effect of the language of the lyrics (native vs foreign) of the music on conversion rates.

Finally, as retailers cannot only choose the pieces of music they play, but also the volume that music is played at, we explore music volume as a possible moderator. Research on the effects of music volume are mixed. Some researchers have found that loud music has positive effects (Morrison et al., 2011), whereas others have found it has negative (Sullivan, 2002) or even non-significant effects (Herrington and Capella, 1996; Hynes and Manson, 2016) on time spent in store. Considering the current investigation, we argue that music volume should not have an effect as store-fit is driven by the type of language of the lyrics, not the loudness of that music; we do not present a formal hypothesis for this null prediction.

In summary, music can vary along many parameters or elements, for example, volume, tempo, pitch and texture, and can be combined to create different retail atmospheres (Bruner, 1990). While many of these parameters have been tested empirically (see Table I; cf. Bruner, 1990), little consideration has been given to the language of the lyrics (native vs foreign) of the music played. Considering these issues, an experimental field study was conducted to test the effects of language of the lyric's choice. Specifically, the authors varied the music in a fashion retailer's store in Mexico for four weeks, tracking time customers spent in the store and whether (or not) they made a purchase.

Methodology

Design and procedure

To test our predictions, a field experiment was conducted in Mexico at a global apparel retailer's store. The study involved a 2 (language of the lyrics of music: native vs foreign) \times 2 (volume: loud vs soft) between-subjects design.

Over the course of two weeks, both the language of the lyrics (first week native (Spanish) vs second week foreign (English)) and volume of music played in the store was randomly varied. To manipulate the language of the lyrics (native vs foreign) of the music, two Top 40 pop song CDs were provided to the retailer to play during the experiment – one sung in Spanish, the other in English. Volume levels (soft vs loud) were operationalized based upon the usual volume of music played in the store (i.e. 65 dB). Explicitly, the authors defined the soft volume condition as music played at 40 dB and the loud music condition as music played at 85 dB. Furthermore, the data collection took place for all hours (11:00 a.m.–8:00 p.m.) and days (Monday–Friday) that the store was open. The store did not run any special promotions during the data collection period.

Upon entering the store, customers were invited to participate in the study. If they agreed, their time in the store was monitored, and they completed a brief survey that included details of their purchase (if they made one) after leaving. The research team approached 482 people as they were leaving the retail store. Approximately half agreed to participate, resulting in a final sample of 241 shoppers (63 percent female, median age $\frac{1}{4}$ 21–30 years). No participants were excluded from any of the analyses.

Measures

For each participant, researchers tracked time in store, gender, age and whether a purchase was made (i.e. conversion rate), as well as the language of the lyrics and loudness of the store music at the time. Following the methodology of Sullivan (2002), time in store was measured by a research assistant as the span of minutes between when customers arrived at the store and the time they left. Following Kim et al. (2007), customer receipts were used to determine if the participant had made a purchase (overall conversion rate was 46.9 percent).

Results

In an initial analysis, we checked for possible confounding effects on shopping time due to gender, age and traffic flow in the store. As these effects were all non-significant, we collapsed across them in subsequent analyses, and they are not discussed further.

Effects of store-fit on time in store and conversion rates

To test the effects of the language of the lyrics and volume of music on time spent in store, a two-way ANOVA was calculated with time spent in store as the dependent variable and language of the lyrics (native vs foreign) of the music and volume of music (loud vs soft) as independent variables. Results indicate that customers spent 5 min longer in the store, on average, indicating greater store-fit was created with music played in a foreign language of the lyrics (M_{Foreign} $\frac{1}{4}$ 21.08 min) than with music played in their native language of the lyrics (native vs foreign) (M_{Native} $\frac{1}{4}$ 16.07 min; $F(1,237) \frac{1}{4}$ 7.65, $p < 0.01$, $r \frac{1}{4}$ 0.18; see Table II), which provides support for H1. Neither the main effect of volume ($F(1,237) \frac{1}{4}$ 0.58, ns), nor the interaction of language of the lyrics (native vs foreign) and volume ($F(1,237) \frac{1}{4}$ 0.10, ns) were significant.

To test the effects of the store-fit and volume of music on conversion rates, a logistic regression model was calculated with customer conversion as the dependent variable and store-fit (i.e. language of the lyrics (native vs foreign) of the music) and volume of music (loud vs soft) as independent variables. The main effect of the language of the lyrics of music was significant (B $\frac{1}{4}$ 1.16, $p < 0.01$, OR $\frac{1}{4}$ 3.18). Customers tended to make purchases more often when music was played in a foreign language of the lyrics (M_{Foreign} $\frac{1}{4}$ 55.08 percent) than when music was played in a native language of the lyrics (M_{Native} $\frac{1}{4}$ 39.02 percent), further supporting H1. More specifically, customers listening to music in a foreign language of the lyrics (English) were 3.18 times more likely to make a purchase than customers listening to music in their native language of the lyrics (Spanish; see Figure 1). Neither volume nor its interaction with language of the lyrics was significant ($p > 0.1$).

Insert Table II. Descriptive statistics

Insert Figure I. Effects of language of the lyrics of music on shopping behaviors

Mediation analysis

As research has consistently found, consumers who spend more time a store are subsequently more likely to make a purchase (Yalch and Spangenberg, 2000). In H2, we predicted that when store-fit was created by playing music in English, customers will spend more time in the store and will also have a higher probability of making a purchase. Using PROCESS 2.0 Model 4 (Hayes, 2012), a series of logistic regression models were built to examine time in store as a potential mediator of the effects of the language of the lyrics (native vs foreign) of music on conversion rates (Baron and Kenny, 1986; see Figure 2). The results indicated that music played in a foreign

language of the lyrics had a significant direct effect on time spent in the store ($b = 5.01$, $p < 0.05$), and time spent in the store directly increased conversion rates ($b = 0.125$, $p < 0.001$). When time in store was not included in the model, music language of the lyrics had a direct effect on conversion rates ($b = 0.65$, $p < 0.05$), but the direct effect of music language of the lyrics became non-significant as a predictor when time in store was added to the model ($b = 0.43$, $p = 0.17$), indicating full mediation. A Sobel (1982) test further confirmed that time in store fully mediates the effect of music language of the lyrics on conversion rates ($z = 2.43$, $p = 0.014$), supporting H2. In our study, foreign music (English, compared to music in native language of the lyrics) increases time in store, which then influences conversion rates.

Insert Figure II. Mediation Model

Discussion

The reported research extends previous studies' findings in an effort to learn more about how the language of the lyrics (native vs foreign) of music influences shoppers' behavior in international retailing contexts. Over the course of a month, the language of the lyrics (native vs foreign) and volume of music played was experimentally varied in a retailer's store in Mexico, with time in store and purchase rates tracked. Specifically, the results indicate that when a global retailer plays music in a foreign language of the lyrics that "fits" with the store's environment (i.e. English), shoppers are more likely to make a purchase. This effect is mediated by greater time spent in the store when English language of the lyric's music is played. Volume of the music played does not affect the influence of store-fit created by the language of the lyrics of music.

These results offer support for MacInnis and Parks' (1991) assertion that music must be fit for the context in which it is employed to enhance persuasion. The results support the assertion by Piller (2001, 2003) and Bhatia (2000) that the use of English can elicit a sense of sophistication, modernity, progress and cosmopolitan identity (cf. Hendriks et al., 2015) that fits with a global retailer's image. Furthermore, the results also support Morrison (2001), who argued that retailers can strategically choose the music played in stores to make a connection with specific target markets

Managerial implications

The purpose of the reported research was to offer retailers insights on how the language of the lyrics (native vs foreign) of music played in stores affects consumers in non-US countries. As retailers continue to look to foreign countries for growth, they often consider pursuing retail joint ventures (Owens and Quinn, 2007) and they end up being faced with an inevitable decision – should we develop a consistent, global brand image or customize our stores to the local culture? Selecting appropriate music is relatively inexpensive for the retailer, yet it can increase sales as it encourages consumers to spend longer in the store and become increasingly more likely to convert and purchase. As

such, the fit between the desired image of the retailer and the language of the lyrics (native vs foreign) and volume of music played in stores is an important consideration.

In an increasingly diverse and global world, the question of how to customize atmospherics according to each country's culture grows in importance. The reported research suggests that although retailers may be tempted to "customize" their store atmospheres with local music as they expand internationally, using English fits better with their global branding and will lead to higher conversion rates. The volume of the music is not consequential to these effects and should be less of a concern for retailers. Managers should also use caution when implementing these results in their own contexts and be sure to track changes in conversion rates, as there are likely many factors that can influence store-fit.

Limitations and future research

This study provides an initial exploration of the impacts of language of the lyrics (native vs foreign) of music and volume, and while the results are interesting, there are several important limitations – retail format, location and genre of music. In the reported research, we explore the effects of English vs Spanish Top 40 music on shopping behavior in a fashion apparel store in Mexico. It is possible that the observed effects will not replicate to other types of retailer formats, such as grocery, superstores or online retailing. Similarly, our research focused on a store in Mexico and effects may not generalize to other countries, due to cultural differences. Finally, it is possible that the language of the lyrics (native vs foreign) of music interacts with genre of music, which we did not consider in the current study. In other words, there may be differences in the effects of language of the lyrics on blues, rock, or classical music genres as compared to Top 40.

The reported study opens several avenues for future research. First, future research should explore whether individual differences in music preferences/tastes moderate the reported effects, as music effects tend to vary by shopper preferences (cf. Yalch and Spangenberg, 1993; Yildirim et al., 2015). It would also be interesting to explore whether effects are moderated by the motivation of the shopper – does the purpose of the trip (e.g. hedonic vs utilitarian), size of purchase or type of purchase (e.g. shopping for something for oneself or a gift for another person) modify the effects of the language of the lyrics (native vs foreign) of music? Similarly, future research should explore the interaction of language of the lyrics (native vs foreign) with other features of the music itself, expanding upon the research reviewed in Table I. In the current study, we found that volume did not interact with language of the lyrics (native vs foreign), but other features could also be explored as possible moderators of the language of the lyrics effect, such as tempo (Eroglu et al., 2005; Milliman, 1982, 1986; Oakes, 2003; Soh et al., 2015) and background or foreground condition (Morrison et al., 2011; Petruzzellis et al., 2014; Yalch and Spangenberg, 1990, 1993). Finally, these effects could be tested in a retailing context. Kim and Stoel (2004) have demonstrated that fit is important online as

well (e.g. informational fit-to-task), which raises the question, how would the language of the lyrics of the background music chosen by retailers for YouTube videos/online ads affect consumers? In conclusion, building store-fit is an important consideration for retail managers.

An attractive, low-cost option to improving store-fit quickly is by varying the music played in the store. By using music played in English, global retailers can create greater store-fit that matches their international image and increase both time spent in the store and overall conversion rates.

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Author	Atmospheric Element Studied	Dependent Variable	Sample Size
Baker, Levy, Grewal (1992)	Ambient cues: Music volume (background-foreground) Lighting (soft-bright) Social cues (number/friendliness of employees)	Arousal Pleasure Willingness to buy	147 undergraduate students
Dube & Morin (2001)	Pleasure intensity to background music (unpleasant-pleasant)	Attitude towards: Servicescape & sales personnel Store evaluation Control Variable: Time perception	196 shoppers, mall outlet
Kellaris & Kent (1992)	Music modality (major, minor, atonal)	Time perception Covariates: Affective evaluation of music	150 undergraduate students
Morrin & Chebat (2005)	Music tempo (slow tempo-no music) Aroma (critic-no scent) Unplanned purchase (yes-no)	Perceive product quality Mood Environment quality Total dollar expenditure	774 shoppers, shopping mall
Morrison, et al (2011)	Music volume (background-foreground) Aroma (cinnamon-vanilla-no specific aroma)	Emotional state (pleasure & arousal) Customer overall satisfaction Time in store Money spent Spend per head	263 customers, local fashion retailer
North, Schilcock & Hargreaves (2003)	Music style (Classical music, pop music, and no music)	Overall drink bill Overall food bill Total spend Total time spend	393 customers, restaurant
Oakes (2003)	Music tempo (fast-slow-no music)	Time perception (waiting time) Overall satisfaction Affective responses Covariates: liked music & tempo appropriateness	335 students
Petruzzellis, Chebat & Palumbo (2014)	Music notoriety/familiarity (famous-not famous)	Consumer emotional responses (feelings, pleasure & arousal) Mall patronage Mall perception	304 customers, shopping mall
Sullivan (2002)	Music Volume (no music-soft-loud) Music popularity (popular-unpopular) Music tempo (fast- slow)	Time perception (meal duration) Level of purchase (food and drink expenditures)	10 meal parties

Sweeny & Wyber (2002)	Music genre (pop-classical) Music tempo (slow-fast) Music volume (background-foreground)	Arousal, pleasure, approach-avoidance Willingness to buy Merchandise quality Covariates: liking and familiarity with music	128 undergraduate students
Willson, 2003	Musical styles (jazz, popular, easy listening and classical, and no music)	Perceived atmosphere and quality of service. Number of drinks and amount of alcohol consumed Total spend Awareness of the music Appropriateness of the music	300 customers restaurant
Yalch & Spangenberg (2000)	Music familiarity (familiar-not familiar)	Product evaluation Time perception Emotional state (pleasure & arousal)	71 undergraduate students

Table I. Review of representative studies

	Frequency	Percentage of sample
Gender		
Male	89	37%
Female	152	63%
Age		
< 14 years	2	8.00%
15 to 20 years	44	18.30%
21 to 25 years	80	32.80%
26 to 30 years	63	25.70%
31 to 35 years	35	14.50%
36 to 40 years	10	4.10%
41 to 45 years	4	17.00%
46 to 50 years	2	0.80%
> 50 years	1	0.40%
Traffic flow in store		
Low	107	44%
High	134	56%
Percentage of Purchase		
Not	128	53.1
Yes	113	46.9
Number of items purchased		
Mean	SD	
2.23	2.29	
Total amount spent		
Mean	SD	
489.37 MXP	359.83	
Total time spent in store		
Mean	SD	
18 min.	15 min.	

Table II. Sample description

Figure 1. Effects of music language on shopping behaviors

Figure 2. Mediation model

		Time in Store (minutes)	Conversion Rate (yes or not)
		<i>M (SD)</i>	Percentage of purchase
Loud	Native (Spanish)	16.38 (12.62)	42%
	Foreign (English)	22.50 (15.91)	70%
Soft	Native	15.51 (13.73)	33%
	Foreign	20.35 (16.79)	47%

Table III. Descriptive statistic for volume, time in store and percentage of purchase